

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Adducts of Bis(acetylacetonato)oxovanadium(IV)

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Some adducts of bis(acetylacetonato)oxovanadium(IV) $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ with bases like *N*-methylformamide (CH_3CONH_2), pyrazine ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}_2$), *N*-methylpyrazine ($\text{CH}_3\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{N}_2$), 3-cyanopyridine (3-CNC₅H₄N), 4-cyanopyridine (4-CNC₅H₄N), collidine ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$) and acridine ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{N}$) have been prepared and characterised.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses (Table I) of all the adducts correspond to the formula $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}$ (L=ligand). All these complexes are light green in colour and stable at room temperature. The complexes are soluble in ethanol, methanol and chloroform. Molar conductance (methanol) values of the complexes were around $4.06-13.09 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$; which indicate

their non-ionic character¹. The magnetic moment values (Table I) of the adducts are slightly higher (1.75–2.10 B.M.) than 1.73 B.M. due to mixing of vanadium $3d_{x^2-y^2}$, $3d_{z^2}$ and $4s$ orbitals^{2,3}; the data correspond to mononuclear complexes with distorted octahedral geometry⁴.

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in two different solvent systems: chloroform and isopropanol-petroleum ether (3:7). In chloroform, the complexes show bands at 674, 597 and 391 nm while in the latter solvent system these bands appear at 751, 590 and 309 nm respectively assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{xz} and $d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transitions. These bands almost fall in the same region as those of $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ except that the bands in the adducts show a slight shift towards higher frequencies. These observations suggest a

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff}^* B.M.
	V	N	
VO(acac) ₂ (HCONHCH ₃)	16.02 (15.74)	4.58 (4.32)	1.75
VO(acac) ₂ (C ₄ H ₄ N ₂)	14.49 (14.77)	8.49 (8.11)	1.96
VO(acac) ₂ (CH ₃ C ₄ H ₃ N ₂)	14.45 (14.20)	7.58 (7.79)	2.07
VO(acac) ₂ (3-CNC ₂ H ₄ N)	14.02 (13.82)	7.21 (7.58)	1.83
VO(acac) ₂ (4-CNC ₂ H ₄ N)	13.74 (13.82)	7.32 (7.58)	1.93
VO(acac) ₂ (C ₈ H ₁₁ N)	13.51 (13.22)	3.62 (3.62)	2.10
VO(acac) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₉ N)	11.63 (11.48)	3.22 (3.15)	1.79

*At 303 K.

distorted octahedral stereochemistry for these complexes⁴.

In pyrazine and collidine complexes, V=O stretching frequency which appears at 995 cm⁻¹ in VO(acac)₂ shifts to a lower value of 971 and 942 respectively pointing to direct coordination of the ligand through nitrogen atom⁶. In VO(acac)₂ N-methylformamide, N-H stretching frequencies occur at 3 090, 3 260 and 3 340 cm⁻¹ as compared to their positions observed in the free ligand at 2 875, 3 165 and 3 285 cm⁻¹ respectively. These changes confirm coordination of the ligand through its nitrogen atom. The remaining complexes show no marked change in V=O stretching frequency. However, some of the bands originating from the ligands in these complexes are shifted to lower frequencies than their original position in the free ligand, suggesting coordination of the ligand through their respective nitrogen atom.

In conclusion, all the complexes are mononuclear, six-coordinate possessing a distorted octahedral geometry.

Experimental

Ligands were obtained commercially and purified by usual methods.

Preparation of the complexes of VO(acac)₂: The complexes were prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of VO(acac)₂ and the required ligand by method-A (for liquid ligands) or method-B (for solid ligands). *Method-A*: The adducts of N-methylformamide, N-methylpyrazine and collidine were prepared by this method. A little excess of the amine than the required amount was intimately mixed with VO(acac)₂ and grounded to dryness to give the desired product. *Method-B*: The complexes of pyrazine, 3-cyanopyridine, 4-cyanopyridine and acridine were prepared by this method. A little excess of the ligand than the required stoichiometric amount was refluxed with VO(acac)₂ in ether. The desired compound was obtained in the form of precipitates on removing the solvent.

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